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Module 1 – Assignment – Briefing Memorandum
Environmental Security of the Municipal and Agricultural Water Supply - City of Kabul, Afghanistan
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Background

Kabul, the capital city of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, is the fifth fastest growing city in the world and supports a growing population of 4.5 million inhabitants (mid-2014); the population is projected to be 9 million by 2057.^{1,2} According to a recent development strategy document, prepared by an international advisory committee, “*Few places in the world face such scarce and alarming water supply and sanitation coverage levels*”.³ Because of poor river water quality and unreliable flow timing of the Kabul River (fed by snow and glacier melt in the Hindu Kush Mountains), Kabul and nearby agriculture operations depend almost entirely on groundwater pumped from a shallow aquifer for their potable, irrigation, and other needs.⁴

Environmental Security Issue – Aquifer Overexploitation

Hydrologists from the US Geological Survey, in collaboration with the US Agency for International Development and the Afghanistan Geological Survey, performed a numerical computer model simulation of groundwater use in the Kabul Basin.⁵ The simulation was done to predict the future water availability for Kabul - considering climate change effects and increasing population.⁶ The results indicate greater than half the existing 1,500 (as of 2010) water wells currently in use will go dry (from falling groundwater levels) due to aquifer overexploitation.⁷

Proposed Policy and Management Interventions (2)

Two interventions are envisioned to help alleviate the predicted severe water shortage. Alternative A will proactively manage the recharge of the water supply aquifer (engineered resource management), mitigating overexploitation. Alternative A may use infiltration basins, constructed along the Kabul River, to capture some of the Spring snow and glacier melt water in the Kabul River, diverting it into on-river infiltration basins to recharge the aquifer.

Alternative B will improve and protect the water quality of the Kabul River. Poor surface water quality has forced the population to rely on groundwater as their water supply source - a program to clean up and protect water quality in the Kabul River will reduce the need to use groundwater, reducing aquifer overexploitation. Consumers will see the Kabul River as a source of safe water. Education outreach for the population stressing the importance of caring for the river will be performed through local Islamic leaders; stewardship of water is consistent with the teachings of the Koran, the governing guidance in the Islamic Republic.⁸

¹ Wolding, H., Abenobar, L., Ali, A., et al., 2015. Islamic Republic of Afghanistan: Preparing the Kabul Managed Aquifer Recharge Project. *Asian Development Bank*, Project Number 48440-002.

² Mack, T.J., Akbari, M., Hanif Ashoor, M., et al., 2010. Conceptual model of water resources in the Kabul Basin, Afghanistan. US Department of the Interior, US Geological Survey. pp. 71

³ ANDS Oversight Committee, 2008. Islamic Republic of Afghanistan National Development Strategy 1387-1391 (2008-2013) A Strategy for Security, Governance, Economic Growth and Poverty Reduction. Islamic Republic of Afghanistan. [online] Available at: http://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/en/IMG/pdf/Afghanistan_National_Development_Strategy_eng.pdf [Accessed: 29 JAN 2016] pp.130

⁴ Wolding, H., Abenobar, L., Ali, A., et al., 2015. Islamic Republic of Afghanistan: Preparing the Kabul Managed Aquifer Recharge Project. *Asian Development Bank*, Project Number 48440-002. Section 2 - Issues

⁵ Mack, T.J., Akbari, M., Hanif Ashoor, M., et al., 2010. Conceptual model of water resources in the Kabul Basin, Afghanistan. US Department of the Interior, US Geological Survey. pp. 71

⁶ *Ibid*, pgs.65-68

⁷ *Ibid*, pp.71

⁸ Faruqui, N.I., Biswas, A.K. and Bino, M.J., 2001. Water management in Islam. Workshop on Water Resources Management in the Islamic World (No. 333.91 W324). IDRC, Ottawa (Canada). pgs. 1, 3, 39; see also pgs. 61, 85

If Alternative A and/or Alternative B is implemented, consumers in and around Kabul would benefit from sustainable quantities of groundwater, and improved quality of surface water in the Kabul River. Also, regarding Alternative B, downstream users may also realize benefits from improved water quality. It is possible downstream users of river flow may experience negative benefits from access to reduce quantities of water, equal to the amount of infiltration.

Not intervening means eventual aquifer resource collapse, leaving millions without a source of safe, reliable water supply – which may also threaten food security, and regional security from mass migration. Those groups and organizations that thrive on chaos and destruction may benefit from resource collapse. Also those with capital who could afford (expensive) deep drilling equipment, water treatment technologies, and logistical support, i.e., tanker trucks, may also benefit as suppliers of potable water – for a price. While the Koran prohibits selling of water, it does permit charging a fair price for value-added services, such as treatment and trucking.⁹

Proposed Action Selection

A rational planning process (RPP) will be used to evaluate each proposed intervention.^{10,11} As part of the RPP evaluations, an alternative of not implementing the intervention, i.e., maintaining the *status quo*, will be considered. Interventions determined to be technically sound, feasible, and beneficial to sustainable water resources management, will be selected for implementation.

Discussion

Each proposed intervention will be examined in detail during the RPP.

Intervention components to be examined include (at a minimum):

- Detailed review and evaluation of the individual project phase
- Project schedule, milestones, completion dates
- Potential for improving water security, resource restoration, and fostering a stewardship culture
- For comparison, each proposed intervention will be compared to a ‘no action’ alternative
- Potential risks to project completion will be evaluated, e.g., insurgency violence, insufficient technical expertise, inclement seasonal weather, and so on

As necessary, during the RPP review, project plans will be revised as new ideas and information are developed.

If sufficient funding is available, the implementation of both interventions is desirable to mitigate the environmental security risk. The two interventions are related and complement each other. Although Alternative A and Alternative B are technically very different, they synergistically have a common anticipated outcome: **improve the sustainability of the water supply aquifer.**

⁹ Faruqi, N.I., Biswas, A.K. and Bino, M.J., 2001. Water management in Islam. Workshop on Water Resources Management in the Islamic World (No. 333.91 W324). IDRC, Ottawa (Canada). pgs.

¹⁰ Dzurik, A.A., 2003. Water resources planning. Lanham, Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield. pgs. 83-111

¹¹ Orth, K.D. and Yoe, C.E., 1997. Planning Primer. US Army Corp of Engineers, Institute for Water Resources